

Effects of 12 Weeks of Tai Chi Intervention in Patients With Chronic Ankle Instability. A Randomized Controlled Trial

David Cruz-Díaz, Kyung-Min Kim, Fidel Hita-Contreras, Marco Bergamin, Agustín Aibar-Almazán, and Antonio Martínez-Amat

Context: Tai Chi is a physical activity modality which is widely practiced over the world. The effectiveness of Tai Chi on postural control and balance has been described in older population, but until recently there are no studies that include patients with chronic ankle instability. **Objectives:** The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of 12 weeks of Tai Chi intervention on dynamic balance and self-reported instability in patients with chronic ankle instability. **Study Design:** A randomized controlled trial was carried out. **Setting:** University physical therapy facility. **Participants:** Fifty-two participants were allocated to an intervention group ($n=26$) based on Tai Chi training or a control group ($n=26$) who received no intervention. **Intervention:** The participants completed 12 weeks of Tai Chi intervention (1 h session/2 times per week) or no intervention in the control group. **Main Outcome Measures:** Outcome measures included postural control and self-reported instability feeling assessed by the Star Excursion Balance Test and the Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool, respectively. **Results:** There was observed significant improvement in all Star Excursion Balance Test reach distances (anterior [$F=6.26, P<.01$]; posteromedial [$F=9.58, P<.01$], and posterolateral [$F=8.42, P<.01$]) in the Tai Chi group with no change in the control group ($P<.01$). The intervention group demonstrated significant improvement on self-reported instability feeling assessed by the Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool questionnaire ($F=21.36, P<.01$). **Conclusion:** The obtained results suggested that 12 weeks of Tai Chi intervention have positive effects on postural control and self-reported instability feeling in patients with chronic ankle instability.

Keywords: postural control, self-reported instability, ankle instability, exercise.

Ankle inversion sprain is one of the most common injuries among patients in the primary health care and emergency system.¹ The most frequent lower-extremity injury in sports practice as well as in the general population, it presents an incidence rate of 600 to 700 per 100,000 persons per years.^{1,2} Most ankle sprains are caused by a sudden inversion movement of the ankle joint, resulting in damage to the lateral ligament complex, the most frequently injured structure.³

After an initial ankle sprain, a high percentage of patients will present residual symptoms such as subjective instability, chronic pain and swelling, frequent episodes of ankle “giving way,” and a high recurrence rate.^{4,5} This chronic condition has been defined as chronic ankle instability (CAI), and can be developed in 40% of sprained ankles, with resprain episodes occurring up to 7 years postinjury.⁶ CAI includes, independently or in combination, a subjective feeling of instability known as functional or perceived ankle instability, and also a degree of mechanical instability linked to joint laxity and impaired arthrokinematics.⁵ CAI alters ankle function producing changes in sports and daily life performance, and may even lead to an increased risk of osteoarthritis.⁷

Chronic ankle instability may be associated with an altered muscle activation ratio, impaired proprioception, and neuromuscular control, which in turn could be linked to impairment in postural balance.^{8,9} An alteration of the nervous system pathways

and sensory inputs has been observed in patients with CAI. This contributes, together with the abovementioned dysfunctions, to balance impairment.^{8,10} It has been reported that some accessory muscle groups (especially in the trunk and hips) are activated in those with CAI as a compensatory strategy to maintain balance.¹⁰ The importance of balance improvement in patients with CAI is well documented in the scientific literature. Manual therapy and exercise have been deemed to be effective in the management of CAI.¹¹ As reported in a recent systematic review,¹² exercise training focusing on balance seems to be superior to other interventions in improving self-reported function in patients with CAI.

Tai Chi is widely spread all over the world, and its benefits on postural balance and lower-extremity strength are supported by several studies.^{13,14} There is a broad consensus among the research community about the effectiveness of Tai Chi in the improvement of balance and postural control in older populations.¹⁵ The most popular style of Tai Chi is known as Yang, which is based on 108 forms (specific Tai Chi movements) which include a wide range of movements that involve center of pressure variations, upper- and lower-limb movements, and deep trunk muscle activation.¹⁶ The practice of this physical activity has been linked to some beneficial effects such as improvements in proprioception, activation of the deep trunk muscles, hip strength, and spatial orientation, all of which could have a positive influence on patients with CAI.¹³⁻¹⁶ However, and to the extent of our knowledge, no studies have looked into how Tai Chi may affect patients with CAI.

For these reasons, the primary purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of this intervention in the improvement of postural balance and subjective instability feeling of patients with CAI. The hypothesis of this study was that a 12-week Tai Chi intervention might lead to enhancements in balance and self-reported instability.

Cruz-Díaz, Hita-Contreras, Aibar-Almazán, and Martínez-Amat are with the Department of Health Sciences, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Jaén, Jaén, Spain. Kim is with the Department of Kinesiology and Sport Sciences, University of Miami, FL. Bergamin is with Sport and Exercise Medicine Division, Department of Medicine, University of Padova, Padova, Italy. Hita-Contreras

(fhita@ujaen.es) is corresponding author.

Methods

Design

This study was a single-blinded randomized controlled trial, with the researcher who assessed the outcomes being blinded as to subject allocation. The independent variable was belonging (or not) to a group subject to a Tai Chi intervention. Outcome variables were postural stability and self-reported ankle instability. The 3 directions (anterior, posterolateral, and posteromedial reach distance) of the Star Excursion Balance Test (SEBT) were measured to determine postural stability, and the Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool (CAIT) was employed to monitor subjective feelings of instability. Both outcomes were assessed before and after 12 weeks of intervention.

Participants

Participants were recruited by posting announcements in the local newspaper and in sport centers. Participation eligibility was consistent with recommendations made by the International Ankle Consortium, and determined by prescreening measures including: (1) a previous episode of ankle sprain in a period of at least 6 months prior to the beginning of the study, (2) a score of 25 or less in the CAIT to confirm current feelings of ankle joint instability, (3) no history of other musculoskeletal injuries in the lower limbs, (4) mental and physical autonomy to participate in Tai Chi classes, and (5) to be able to display physical activity for at least 90 minutes per week. Exclusion criteria for participants were (1) self-reported vestibular or balance-related dysfunction, (2) recent surgery, or (3) already being a Tai Chi practitioner. This study was approved by the human ethics committee of the University of Jaén. Informed

consent forms were obtained from all participants who accepted to be enrolled in the study.

Patients who met the inclusion criteria were randomly assigned to either an intervention group, who undertook a Tai Chi training program for 12 weeks with 2 sessions per week, or a control group who did not receive any form of exercise intervention (no exercise) during the same period (Figure 1). An independent assessor carried out group allocation using a list of computer-generated numbers. Patients were excluded if they missed more than 3 sessions during the 12-week program.

Procedures (Independent Variables)

The independent variables used in this study were *treatment* (12 wk of Tai Chi training) for the intervention group and *no treatment* for the control group. Participants allocated to the Tai Chi group underwent a 60-minute Tai Chi exercise session twice a week. The exercise session consisted of a warm-up with articular mobility drills, balance, and stretching, followed by the main Tai Chi session based on the basic 24 forms (specific Tai Chi movements) of the Yang style, whose movements are performed along 4 directions from both sides of the body. The included motions were slow movements of the whole body with controlled displacements in all directions including rotations and 1-leg stances. This technique places great importance on keeping close control of body position at all times, while keeping good balance. Therefore, a semisquat position is usually maintained, with soft changes in the center of gravity from one leg to the other, and a focus on diaphragmatic breathing in coordination with the movements of legs, trunk, and arms. Finally, a 10-minute relaxation period took place at the end of each Tai Chi training session (Figure 2).

Figure 1 — Flowchart of the study design and participants follow-up through the trial.

Figure 2 — Tai Chi Yang style forms examples. Differences in center of gravity and weight distribution between both legs during Tai Chi intervention.

Control Group Wait List. Participants assigned to the control group were advised to maintain their usual activity, and not to engage in any form of exercise treatment for CAI, while the study took place. However, they were offered the opportunity to participate in the Tai Chi program after being released from this study.

Outcome Measures (Dependent Variables). The dependent variables analyzed in this study were (1) postural stability (main outcome), quantified by the SEBT and (2) self-reported feeling of instability, measured by the CAIT.

As for postural stability, the SEBT involves a single-leg stance on the affected leg with the opposite leg reaching to the maximal distance without losing single-leg balance on the affected leg.¹⁷ The SEBT has proved to be useful in detecting deficits in postural control in patients with CAI.^{17–19} The simplified version of the SEBT was used, with the anterior, posteromedial, and posterolateral reach distances being assessed for statistical analysis.²⁰ The standard test was used, which involves subjects in their stockinged feet, hands on hips, standing on the affected lower-extremity placed on the center of the grid. Subjects were instructed to maintain the stability of the affected leg, while trying to reach the further distance with the other leg with a slight toe touch but without losing balance. Each subject performed 4 practice trials in each of the 3 directions to familiarize themselves with the procedure.¹⁹ The order of the 3 directions they had to reach for was randomly assigned. Three trials were performed in each direction with a 15-second rest period between trials, and the averages (cm) were used for statistical analysis. Trials were repeated if participants lost balance including compensating for body motion, separating their hands from the hips, lifting any part of the foot under analysis, or placing weight when touching down with the contralateral foot.

Regarding subjective feelings of instability, the Spanish version of the CAIT²¹ was employed. The CAIT is scored on a 30-point scale in which higher scores represent ankle stability and values ≤ 25 represent ankle instability.²² Given the lack of an objective gold standard of assessment to determine the presence of CAI, CAIT is recommended by the International Ankle Consortium,²³ and has been deemed to be a valid and reliable measurement tool capable of discriminating between patients with and without CAI.²² The Spanish version of the CAIT has high internal consistency (Cronbach $\alpha = .766$) and reliability (intraclass correlation coefficient = .979; 95% confidence interval, .958–.990).²¹ A recent study has established a minimal detectable change score of 3 or greater on CAIT²⁴ that can be used to determine the effectiveness of an intervention for CAI.

Statistical Analyses

To compare the between-groups variables, Student *t* test or its nonparametric equivalent, the Mann–Whitney *U* test, were used. To assess differences in SEBT and CAIT (dependent variables) between evaluation times within-groups, a 2 (group) by 2 (time) analysis of variance with repeated measures was used (or its nonparametric alternative, the Friedman test). Chi-square was used to compare descriptive data of the participants. Statistical analysis was performed using the SPSS software (version 20.0; SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL). The alpha level was set at $P < .05$ for all tests.

A required number of 21 participants with CAI per group were estimated to ensure a power of 0.80 at a significance level of 95% based on a minimal detectable change of 4.28 cm in the posterolateral direction of SEBT,²⁵ but 26 participants per group were enrolled in the study due to a possible dropout rate of 20%.

Results

A total of 52 participants with CAI were enrolled in the study, with 26 assigned to the Tai Chi group and 26 to the control group (Table 1). Three participants did not complete the study: 1 participant in the Tai Chi group missed more than 3 exercise sessions and 2 participants in the control group did not attend a postintervention testing session. The adherence rate in the intervention group was very high, with an overall 94% attendance. A total of 49 participants completed the study and were included for statistical analysis (Figure 1).

Both groups were similar at baseline for all dependent and sociodemographic variables (Table 1). A significant group \times condition interaction in the Tai Chi group was observed for all SEBT reach distances after 12 weeks of Tai Chi intervention, compared with baseline performance with $F = 6.26$ ($P < .01$) for the anterior reach distance, $F = 9.58$ ($P < .01$) for the posteromedial direction, and $F = 8.42$ ($P < .01$) for the posterolateral direction. No change was observed in the control group (Table 2). Self-reporting instability measured with CAIT showed significant improvement in the intervention group and no change in the control group ($F = 21.36$, $P < .01$; see Table 2 and Figure 3).

Discussion

Our results suggest that 12 weeks of Tai Chi practice are effective in managing patients with CAI. Participants included in the intervention group reported significant improvement in postural control and self-reported feeling of instability.

Until recently, this has been the first study looking into how Tai Chi practice affects patients with CAI, and therefore, we were unable to compare our results with those of any previous research. However, there are some studies whose findings could be extrapolated to CAI given the similarities between the interventions carried out.

Regarding balance, some studies have shown how Tai Chi improves postural balance by reducing postural sway and enhancing proprioception.²⁶ Tai Chi is based on a sequence of movements performed, while maintaining balance. Several movements are performed which involve the translation of body weight between both legs, body rotation, and single-leg stances.¹³ Tai Chi movements may share some common features with balance training exercises, which have been reported as beneficial for CAI patients regarding balance and sensorimotor restoration, and which could

be related to altered mechanics during functional tasks and self-reported impaired function.¹¹ The flexed position in the lower limbs during Tai Chi practice is possibly linked to improvements in the range of motion of the ankle joint, as well as in the ankle joint torque force, identified as a contributing factor for postural balance.¹¹ In addition, it has been found that Tai Chi enhances reactive postural response in an older population with balance dysfunction due to muscle activation delay, which is a common deficit in those with CAI.²⁷

Table 1 Sociodemographic Characteristics at Baseline

	Tai Chi group (n = 26)	Control group (n = 26)	P value
	35.4 (10.46)	36.3 (11.98)	.72
Gender			
Male	11 (42.3%)	12 (46.15%)	.52
Female	15 (67.7%)	14 (53.85%)	
Height, cm	172 (8.5)	171 (7.2)	.14
Weight, kg	65.54 (7.08)	66.02 (6.95)	.52
Education			
Primary	1 (3.85%)		.81
Secondary	14 (53.85%)	14 (53.85%)	
University	11 (42.3%)	12 (46.15%)	
Marital status			
Single	11 (53.85%)	14 (41.17%)	.65
Married	14 (41.17%)	12 (46.55%)	
Divorced	1 (3.85%)		
Occupational status			
Full-time worker	14 (53.85%)	12 (46.15%)	.72
Part-time worker	8 (30.76%)	8 (30.76%)	
Unemployed	4 (15.38%)	6 (23.07%)	
Affected ankle			
Left	8 (30.76%)	7 (26.92%)	.82
Right	18 (69.23%)	19 (73.07%)	
CAIT	17.6 (2.1)	18.3 (2.3)	.32
SEBT, cm			
Anterior	92.42 (10.2)	93.35 (5.4)	.58
Posterolateral	86.46 (7.9)	86.98 (6.84)	.91
Posteromedial	86.4 (7.69)	87.01 (3.4)	.89

Abbreviations: CAIT, Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool; SEBT, Star Excursion Balance Test. Note: Values are presented as mean (SD).

In this study, participants included in the Tai Chi group showed significant improvement in all measured directions of the SEBT after 12 weeks of intervention, while no change was observed in the control group ($P < .01$). These results could in turn be supported by a recent study by Wang et al,¹⁴ who reported tibialis anterior neuromuscular reaction improvement during lateral perturbation in older Tai Chi habitual practitioners. In addition to tibialis anterior neuromuscular enhancement due to a Tai Chi intervention, Zhou et al²⁸ reported an increase in muscle strength of the lower limbs after Tai Chi practice. Strength gains may contribute to improving postural stability and self-reported instability, in agreement with the results obtained in this study. On the other hand, Liu et al²⁹ conducted a study comparing the effects of Tai Chi and proprioceptive training on the neuromuscular function of the ankle in an older population, but failed to find any differences in strength after a Tai Chi intervention. However, a major finding of that study was the observed improvement on joint position sense, with similar results in the proprioceptive training and the Tai Chi group. This study was not performed in patients affected by CAI, but their data agree with our results and suggest that improvements in proprioception and neuromuscular control may have a positive influence on CAI. Improvements in ankle joint muscle onset activation, muscle cocontraction, as well as the strategies regarding the center of gravity distribution during Tai Chi training, could be linked to improved proprioception in patients with CAI. Until recently, this has been the first study focusing on the effects that Tai Chi practice may have on the postural balance of patients with CAI, and our results suggest that Tai Chi could be a useful and safe

Figure 3 — CAIT scores at baseline and after 12 weeks of intervention. CAIT indicates Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool. * $P < .001$.

Table 2 Comparison of SEBT and CAIT Between Groups

Outcome measure	Tai Chi group		Control group		P value
	Preintervention	After 12 wk	Preintervention	After 12 wk	
SEBT					
Anterior, cm	92.42 (10.2)	97.76 (9.9) ^{a,b}	93.35 (5.4)	93.98 (4.8)	<.001
Posteromedial, cm	86.4 (7.69)	92.86 (5.6) ^{a,b}	87.01 (3.4)	87.65 (4.2)	<.001
Posterolateral, cm	86.46 (7.9)	96.86 (9.3) ^{a,b}	86.98 (6.84)	88.01 (4.2)	<.001
CAIT	17.6 (2.1)	28.4 (2.4) ^{a,b}	18.3 (2.3)	18.5 (1.8)	<.001

Abbreviations: CAIT, Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool; SEBT, Star Excursion Balance Test. Note: Values are presented as mean (SD).

^aSignificant changes within groups. ^bSignificant changes between groups.

therapeutic approach for the management of this population group, given the high adherence rate observed in the intervention group.

Subjective feelings of instability (which are linked to functional instability) are widely spread among those with CAI. At the beginning of the intervention CAIT scores were similar in both groups, with a mean score of 17.6 and 18.3 points in the Tai Chi and control groups, respectively. After 12 weeks of Tai Chi training, participants included in this group improved their CAIT scores to the point that they could be considered healthy.²³ Minimal detectable change of CAIT scores, when used to assess the effectiveness of an intervention over time, has been set at ≥ 3 points,²⁴ and; therefore, the results of this study should be considered clinically relevant. After the Tai Chi intervention, patients reported improvement in postural stability assessed with the SEBT and improved subjective instability feeling as revealed by CAIT scores. Tai Chi movements promote the proper distribution of the center of mass between both legs during dynamic tasks performed in all directions, with particular attention to postural alignment. These movements may lead to enhancements in postural control, stability strategies, and appropriate force distribution between the lower-limb joints, which in turn may be linked to improvements in all reach distances of the SEBT. Patients with CAI developed alternative balance strategies, with predominant hip muscles activation.¹⁰ The strengthening of hips has been shown to bring about benefits in postural balance and self-reported instability in patients with CAI.³⁰ The semisquat position of Tai Chi, the lateral movement transitions, the lumbopelvic stabilization, and the reeducation of foot support with proper alignment may all play an important role in the observed improvement in both dynamic stability and self-reported instability.

Increased scores in SEBT reach distances could be linked to the improvement of ankle range of motion,¹¹ which is usually limited in patients with CAI.²² In this study, ankle range of motion has not been included as an outcome measure, but improvements were visually observed during Tai Chi practice and SEBT assessment. Long-term effects of Tai Chi should be controlled with the inclusion of a follow-up period in future randomized controlled trials.

Limitations and Further Research

The main limitation of the study was the lack of a follow-up period to assess how the observed improvements are maintained over time in patients with CAI. However, and considering our positive findings, the inclusion of some variables related to CAI, such as ankle range of motion and some additional postural control measures, is recommended. The inclusion of force plate platforms could provide additional data, despite the fact that some force platforms provide data concerning force magnitude but not center of pressure, which is related to postural stability. On the other hand, previous studies have stated that a more functionally oriented test, such as SEBT, provides more reliable and valid information in those with CAI. Improvements have been reported in lower-limb strength of an older population after Tai Chi training, but the influence of Tai Chi in a CAI-affected population has not been studied. Future research should look into electromyographic activity during Tai Chi practice as well as into muscle strength gains after the intervention, with special attention to hip adductors, peroneus, and tibialis muscles.

Conclusion

Tai Chi is a low-impact physical activity, widely spread all over the world. Its benefits have been reported for different population groups. Nevertheless, until recently this has been the first study

focusing on the effectiveness of Tai Chi in patients with CAI. Participants included in the Tai Chi group showed significant improvement in postural stability and self-reported feeling of instability, with no reported adverse events. Tai Chi might be recommended as an effective and easy to apply intervention in the management of patients affected with CAI, with the additional benefit of the possibility of group class performance.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the Dharma Institute of Martial Arts and Oriental Studies for its support during the Tai Chi intervention, and especially Kim Li and Fabrizio Monachino. Furthermore, all researchers involved in this study would like to express their gratitude to the participants of this study for their commitment and willingness. No competing financial interests exist. The authors would like to express their gratitude to Ángela Molina for her cooperation in the recruitment process, and especially to the patients who participated in the study. The authors certify that no party having a direct interest in the results of the research supporting this article has or will confer a benefit on us or on any organization with which the authors are associated and, if applicable, the authors also certify all financial and material support for this research (eg, NIH or NHS grants).

References

1. Fong D, Hong Y, Chan L, Yung P, Chan K. A systematic review of ankle injury and ankle sprain in sports. *Sports Med.* 2007;37(1): 73–94. PubMed ID: [17190537](#) doi:[10.2165/00007256-200737010-00006](#)
2. Bridgman SA, Clement D, Downing A, Walley G, Phair I, Maffulli N. Population based epidemiology of ankle sprains attending accident and emergency units in the West Midlands of England, and a survey of UK practice for severe ankle sprains. *Emerg Med J.* 2003;20:508–510. PubMed ID: [14623833](#) doi:[10.1136/emj.20.6.508](#)
3. Kerkhoffs GM, Rowe BH, Assendelft WJ, Kelly KD, Struijs PA, van Dijk CN. Immobilisation and functional treatment for acute lateral ankle ligament injuries in adults. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2013;(3):CD003762.
4. Delahunt E, O'Driscoll J, Moran K. The effects of taping and exercise on ankle joint movements in subjects with functional instability (FI) of the ankle joint during a jump down. *J Foot Ankle Surg.* 2008; 1(suppl 1):O7.
5. Hiller CE, Kilbreath SL, Refshauge KM. Chronic ankle instability: evolution of the model. *J Athl Train.* 2011;46(2):133–141. PubMed ID: [21391798](#) doi:[10.4085/1062-6050-46.2.133](#)
6. Konradsen L, Bech L, Ehrenbjerg M, Nickelsen T. Seven years follow-up after ankle inversion trauma. *Scand J Med Sci Sports.* 2002;12:129–135. PubMed ID: [12135444](#) doi:[10.1034/j.1600-0838.2002.02104.x](#)
7. Tregouret P, Merland F, Horodyski MB. A comparison of the effects of ankle taping styles on biomechanics during ankle inversion. *Ann Phys Rehabil Med.* 2013;56:113–122. doi:[10.1016/j.rehab.2012.12.001](#)
8. Lee HJ, Lim KB, Jung TH, Kim DY, Park KR. Changes in balancing ability of athletes with chronic ankle instability after foot orthotics application and rehabilitation exercises. *Ann Rehabil Med.* 2013;37:523–533. PubMed ID: [24020033](#) doi:[10.5535/arm.2013.37.4.523](#)
9. Kim KM, Hart JM, Saliba SA, Hertel J. Modulation of the fibularis longus Hoffmann reflex and postural instability associated with

- chronic ankle instability. *J Athl Train*. 2016;51(8):637–643. PubMed ID: [27583692](#) doi:[10.4085/1062-6050-51.10.05](#)
10. Rios JL, Gorges AL, dos Santos MJ. Individuals with chronic ankle instability compensate for their ankle deficits using proximal musculature to maintain reduced postural sway while kicking a ball. *Hum Mov Sci*. 2015;43:33–44. PubMed ID: [26189152](#) doi:[10.1016/j.humov.2015.07.001](#)
 11. Cruz-Díaz D, Lomas Vega R, Ozuma-Pérez MC, et al. Effects of joint mobilization on chronic ankle instability: a randomized controlled trial. *Disabil Rehabil*. 2015;37:601–610. PubMed ID: [24989067](#) doi:[10.3109/09638288.2014.935877](#)
 12. Kosik KB, McCann RS, Terada M, Gribble PA. Therapeutic interventions for improving self-reported function in patients with chronic ankle instability: a systematic review. *Br J Sports Med*. 2017;51(2):105–112. PubMed ID: [27806951](#) doi:[10.1136/bjsports-2016-096534](#)
 13. Lan C, Lai JS, Chen SY. Tai Chi Chuan: an ancient wisdom on exercise and health promotion. *Sports Med*. 2002;32(4):217–224. PubMed ID: [11929351](#) doi:[10.2165/00007256-200232040-00001](#)
 14. Wang SJ, Xu DQ, Li JX. Effects of regular Tai Chi practice and jogging on neuromuscular reaction during lateral postural control in older people. *Res Sports Med*. 2017;25(1):111–117. PubMed ID: [27868426](#) doi:[10.1080/15438627.2016.1258649](#)
 15. Wu G. Evaluation of the effectiveness of Tai Chi for improving balance and preventing falls in the older population—a review. *J Am Geriatr Soc*. 2002;50(4):746–754. PubMed ID: [11982679](#) doi:[10.1046/j.1532-5415.2002.50173.x](#)
 16. Jwing-Ming Y. *Tai Chi Chuan Classical Yang Style: The Complete Form Qigong*. 2nd ed. YMAA Publication Center; Wolfeboro EE.UU 2010.
 17. Olmsted LC, Carcia CR, Hertel J, Shultz SJ. Efficacy of the Star Excursion Balance Tests in detecting reach deficits in subjects with chronic ankle instability. *J Athl Train*. 2002;37:501–506. PubMed ID: [12937574](#)
 18. Plisky PJ, Gorman PP, Butler RJ, Kiesel KB, Underwood FB, Elkins B. The reliability of an instrumented device for measuring components of the Star Excursion Balance Test. *North Am J Sport Phys Ther*. 2009;4:92–99.
 19. Gribble PA, Hertel J, Plisky P. Using the Star Excursion Balance Test to assess dynamic postural-control deficits and outcomes in lower extremity injury: a literature and systematic review. *J Athl Train*. 2012;47:339–357. PubMed ID: [22892416](#) doi:[10.4085/1062-6050-47.3.08](#)
 20. Hertel J, Braham RA, Hale SA, Olmsted-Kramer LC. Simplifying the Star Excursion Balance Test: analyses of subjects with and without chronic ankle instability. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther*. 2006;36(3):131–137. PubMed ID: [16596889](#) doi:[10.2519/jospt.2006.36.3.131](#)
 21. Cruz-Díaz D, Hita-Contreras F, Lomas-Vega R, Osuna-Pérez MC, Martínez-Amat A. Cross-cultural adaptation and validation of the Spanish version of the Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool (CAIT): an instrument to assess unilateral chronic ankle instability. *Clin Rheumatol*. 2013;32(1):91–98. doi:[10.1007/s10067-012-2095-0](#)
 22. Hiller CE, Refshauge KM, Bundy AC, Herbert RD, Kilbreath SL. The Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool: a report of validity and reliability testing. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2006;87:1235–1241. PubMed ID: [16935061](#) doi:[10.1016/j.apmr.2006.05.022](#)
 23. Gribble PA, Delahunt E, Bleakley C, et al. Selection criteria for patients with chronic ankle instability in controlled research: a position statement of the International Ankle Consortium. *J Athl Train*. 2014;49(1):121–127. PubMed ID: [24377963](#) doi:[10.4085/1062-6050-49.1.14](#)
 24. Wright CJ, Linens SW, Cain MS. Establishing the minimal clinical important difference and minimal detectable change for the Cumberland Ankle Instability Tool. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2017;98(9):1806–1811. PubMed ID: [28137476](#) doi:[10.1016/j.apmr.2017.01.003](#)
 25. Hoch MC, Anreatta RD, Mullineaux DR, et al. Two-week joint mobilization intervention improves self-reported function, range of motion, and dynamic balance in those with chronic ankle instability. *J Orthop Res*. 2012;30(11):1798–1804. PubMed ID: [22610971](#) doi:[10.1002/jor.22150](#)
 26. Gauchard CG, Gangloff P, Jeandel C, Perrin PP. Influence of regular proprioceptive and bioenergetic physical activities on balance control in elderly women. *J Gerontol*. 2003;58(9):M846–M850. doi:[10.1093/gerona/58.9.M846](#)
 27. Gatts SK, Woollacott MH. Neural mechanisms underlying balance improvement with short term Tai Chi training. *Aging Clin Exp Res*. 2006;18(1):7–19. PubMed ID: [16608131](#) doi:[10.1007/BF03324635](#)
 28. Zhou M, Peng N, Dai Q, Li HW, Shi RG, Huang W. Effect of Tai Chi on muscle strength of the lower extremities in the elderly. *Chin J Integr Med*. 2016;22(11):861–866. PubMed ID: [26015074](#) doi:[10.1007/s11655-015-2104-7](#)
 29. Liu J, Wang XQ, Zheng JJ, et al. Effects of Tai Chi versus proprioception exercise program on neuromuscular function of the ankle in elderly people: a randomized controlled trial. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2012;2012:265486. PubMed ID: [23346195](#)
 30. Webster KA, Gribble PA. Functional rehabilitation interventions for chronic ankle instability: a systematic review. *J Sport Rehabil*. 2010;19:98–114. PubMed ID: [20231748](#) doi:[10.1123/jsr.19.1.98](#)

AUTHOR PROOF